

Interpreting and Extending the Maximum Ratio Test of Unacceptability

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Abstract

Tsao and Wright (1983) proposes the use of a statistic called the “maximum ratio” to assess the reliability of K estimates $\hat{\theta}_1, \dots, \hat{\theta}_K$ of an unknown population parameter θ . This statistic can be used to test whether one of these estimates is outside of an “acceptable” region, whose radius is a multiple α of the unknown true parameter θ . Because θ is unknown, it is difficult to know whether a large α value reflects a large error in the underlying metric, or just a large proportion of a small θ . This paper generalizes the maximum ratio test to multiple dimensions, considers some broad approaches for selecting an α value for this test in the absence of knowledge of θ , applies the test to five estimates of the population proportions for eight demographic subgroups within the United States, and visualizes the results. We then repeat the process after intentionally introducing errors into one of the estimates. This paper is abridged from Hall (2024).

Key Words: inaccuracy, quality of data, comparison of estimates, federal statistical issues

1. Introduction

Scientists often find themselves comparing several competing, positive estimates of the same unknown positive parameter θ . When we don't know which is the best, it is common to evaluate a collection of such estimates $\{\hat{\theta}_1, \dots, \hat{\theta}_K\}$ by how close they are to each other. Tsao and Wright (1983) suggest a metric called the “maximum ratio” as a measure of the “closeness” of a set of such estimates. The maximum ratio is defined as the range of the estimates divided by the minimum:

$$M = \frac{\hat{\theta}_{(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{(1)}}{\hat{\theta}_{(1)}}$$

Whether due to bias or variability, estimates can be close to each other but far from the unknown truth. To address this concern, Tsao and Wright (1983) show that the maximum ratio can be used to evaluate whether any of the estimates are “too far” from the true value θ that they are estimating. We describe the method Tsao and Wright (1983) propose for this below.

2. Maximum Ratio Test of Unacceptability

Tsao and Wright (1983) use the maximum ratio to produce the “maximum ratio test of unacceptability,” which we abbreviate to “the maximum ratio test” (or MRT) for the remainder of the paper. The maximum ratio test identifies sets of estimates for which at least one estimate is “unacceptable.” Formally, an estimate $\hat{\theta}$ is unacceptable when $|\theta - \hat{\theta}| > \alpha$ for some α such that $0 < \alpha < 1$. In other words, an unacceptable estimate is at least $\alpha \times 100\%$ of θ away from θ . For a given value M_0 of the maximum ratio, the maximum ratio test statistic $T(M_0)$ is defined as

$$T(M_0) = \frac{M_0}{M_0 + 2}$$

When $T(M_0) > \alpha$, then at least one $\hat{\theta}_k$ in the set is unacceptable in the sense defined above.

Equivalently, when $T(M_0) > \alpha$ then at least one estimate $\hat{\theta}_k$ in the set will fall outside of the interval $[\theta - \alpha\theta, \theta + \alpha\theta]$. When $T(M_0) \leq \alpha$, there is not enough evidence to conclude that at least one of the estimates is “unacceptable.”

2.1 Multidimensional Maximum Ratio Test

Wright (2013) gives a detailed geometric explanation of the maximum ratio, and extends it to two dimensions. For the remainder of this paper, we will denote vectors using bold italicized symbols so that, for example, θ denotes a scalar parameter and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ denotes a vector parameter. In the two-dimensional case, assume that $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1, \theta_2]^T$ and there are K estimates $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k = [\hat{\theta}_{1,k}, \hat{\theta}_{2,k}]^T$ of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ where $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. In this notation, $\hat{\theta}_{g,k}$ is the k th estimate for parameter θ_g , where $g \in \{1, 2\}$. In this circumstance, Wright (2013) defines the two-dimensional maximum ratio as

$$M = \frac{\sqrt{(\hat{\theta}_{1,(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{1,(1)})^2 + (\hat{\theta}_{2,(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{2,(1)})^2}}{\sqrt{\hat{\theta}_{1,(1)}^2 + \hat{\theta}_{2,(1)}^2}}$$

where $\hat{\theta}_{g,(k)}$ is the k th order statistic of the K estimates for parameter g . Wright (2013) also proposes a two-dimensional maximum ratio test based on this two-dimensional maximum ratio and a different test statistic. However, we were unable to verify that this version of the two-dimensional maximum ratio test has the specified α level for all possible values of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

Instead, we propose a multidimensional maximum ratio test statistic heavily inspired by the work done in both Wright (2013) and Tsao and Wright (1983). First, assume that we have an unknown G dimensional parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The g th element of this parameter is denoted θ_g where $g \in \{1, \dots, G\}$. We also have K estimates of each parameter. We denote the k th estimate of element g as $\hat{\theta}_{g,k}$, and the k th order statistic of the estimates for parameter g as $\hat{\theta}_{g,(k)}$. We assume that each element θ_g of the parameter and each estimate $\hat{\theta}_{g,k}$ of that element is non-negative.

Given these assumptions, we define the "multidimensional maximum ratio" as

$$M = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^G (\hat{\theta}_{g,(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)})^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^G (\hat{\theta}_{g,(1)})^2}} = \frac{\|\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{(K)} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{(1)}\|}{\|\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{(1)}\|}$$

where we define $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{(1)} = [\hat{\theta}_{1,(1)}, \dots, \hat{\theta}_{G,(1)}]^T$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{(K)} = [\hat{\theta}_{1,(K)}, \dots, \hat{\theta}_{G,(K)}]^T$, and $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm.

For a particular value M_0 of this M , we use the same test statistic proposed in Tsao and Wright (1983) to conduct the multidimensional maximum ratio test:

$$T(M_0) = \frac{M_0}{M_0 + 2}$$

As before, if $T(M_0) > \alpha$, then some combination of our estimates $\hat{\theta}_{g,k}$ is unacceptable (See Main Result in the Appendix 7.1.2 of Hall (2024)). In the two-dimensional case, this would mean that some combination $[\hat{\theta}_{1,k_1}, \hat{\theta}_{2,k_2}]^T$ of the first element from estimate $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{k_1}$ and the second element from estimate $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{k_2}$ falls outside a circle centered at (θ_1, θ_2) with radius $\alpha\sqrt{\theta_1^2 + \theta_2^2}$.

Analogously, in a higher dimensional example, we would conclude that some combination $[\hat{\theta}_{1,k_1}, \dots, \hat{\theta}_{G,k_G}]^T$ of our K estimates for the elements of our G -dimensional parameter falls outside of a (hyper)sphere centered at $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ with radius $\alpha\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$. Formally, our result (see Main Result in Appendix 7.1.2 of Hall (2024)) shows that if $T(M_0) > \alpha$ then we can find some point $\boldsymbol{v} = [\hat{\theta}_{1,k_1}, \dots, \hat{\theta}_{G,k_G}]^T$ where $k_1, \dots, k_G \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ such that $\|\boldsymbol{v} - \boldsymbol{\theta}\| > \alpha\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$. When $T(M_0) \leq \alpha$, there is not enough evidence to conclude that one of the estimates is unacceptable in this sense. We provide a demonstration of this result in the Appendix.

2.2 Interpreting the Maximum Ratio Test

Note that the maximum ratio test is a *deterministic* test, not a probabilistic one. It is valid regardless of the distribution of the estimates and does not require the specification of a significance level. The

downside of this generality is that we can never know what the true value of θ (or $\boldsymbol{\theta}$) is, and this uncertainty can make α difficult to interpret.

For a given value M_0 of the maximum ratio and any α between 0 and 1, the maximum ratio test concludes that at least one estimate is unacceptable when $T(M_0) > \alpha$. This is equivalent to stating that for any α , if $0 < \alpha < T(M_0)$, then at least one of the estimates is at least $\alpha \times \theta$ (or $\alpha \times \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$) units away from θ (or $\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$). Colloquially, we might say that at least one of the estimates is at least $T(M_0) \times \theta$ (or $T(M_0) \times \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$) away from the truth.

For example, in the one-dimensional case if $T(M_0) > 0.5$ and $\theta = 2$, then at least one of our estimates is at least 1 unit away from the true value. If instead $\theta = 10,000,000$, then at least one of our estimates is off by at least 5,000,000 units! In many contexts the first scenario is acceptable, while the second is not. Similarly, an analyst might interpret $T(M_0)$ as a statistic meaning "the largest α for which we would *not* conclude that at least one $\hat{\theta}_k$ is unacceptable." If θ is very small, the analyst might take a large $T(M_0)$ value as evidence that one of the estimates is of poor quality, when in fact the error $\alpha \times \theta$ is reasonable.

To make the maximum ratio test useful in such circumstances, it is helpful to relate the α value associated with $T(M_0)$ to a range of possible $\alpha \times \theta$ error values. Analogously, in the multidimensional case we want to relate the α value associated with $T(M_0)$ to a range of possible $\alpha \times \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$ values. In this paper we explore three simple approaches to this task and use them to compare five estimates of eight state-level population proportions within each US state using the one-dimensional and multidimensional maximum ratios.

3. Data and Methods

To calculate the maximum ratio, we need a collection of competing estimates of the same underlying parameter. In this example, our parameters are the 2021 population proportions of the following 8 demographic subgroups in each state (and the District of Columbia):

- Non-Hispanic White Alone
- Non-Hispanic Black Alone
- Non-Hispanic Asian Alone
- Non-Hispanic Native Hawaiian / Pacific Islander Alone
- Non-Hispanic American Indian / Alaska Native (AIAN) Alone
- Non-Hispanic Some Other Race Alone
- Non-Hispanic Multiracial
- Hispanic of Any Race

These subgroups partition each state, such that the total state population is equal to the sum of all eight state subgroup population totals.

The subgroup population proportions in each state are our unknown parameters in this study. If we treat the parameters for each subgroup as one-dimensional, we have parameters in 51 different geographies for these 8 demographic subgroups. This gives us a total of $51 \times 8 = 408$ different parameters to estimate. Because the population proportions across the 8 subgroups for a state will sum to one and are hence dependent, we do a second set of analyses that consider the vector of these proportions as a single parameter. In this case, we will have 51 unknown 8-dimensional parameters instead of 408 1-dimensional parameters.

For each parameter we apply the maximum ratio to evaluate $K=5$ estimates, derived from a combination of three data sources. All the data sources provide estimates of the population total of each demographic subgroup. We estimate the population proportions of each subgroup by dividing the subgroup's estimated population in each state by the total population of that state.

The first set of estimates of population totals is sourced from the "Total Population by Race and Hispanic or Latino Origin" (Table B03002) estimate from the 2021 5-year American Community

Survey (ACS). The American Community Survey is a well-established sample survey produced by the U.S. Census Bureau which has collected and published information about American demographics since 2005 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The last four estimates of totals are based on demonstration products from the Census Bureau's Continuous Count Study that estimate the population total of each state based on administrative records available to the Census Bureau (Brown et al, 2024). These four estimate types are rounded before use to limit the risk of inappropriate disclosure. The Census Disclosure Review Board (DRB) clearance number associated with the release of these rounded estimates is CBDRB-FY24-0264.

Administrative records are data that are gathered during government business and/or used to provide services to the public, such as IRS tax filings or Social Security records. The first three of these four estimates are counts of individuals included within a collection of administrative data sources available to the US Census Bureau in 2021. These are referred to as the Annual Administrative Record Population Estimates (AAPE). The people included in these records are linked to addresses within the states according to three separate methods A, B, and C, which correspond to our three experimental metrics for state population. In brief, these methods are distinguished by whether they use information with missing Census tract information, and whether they assume that an individual's address of residence is included in the AAPE data. Method C includes all the AAPE records by imputing census tract geocodes when they are missing, while Methods A and B exclude any individuals from the AAPE data without tract geocodes rather than imputing them. Method A attempts to adjust probabilities that a given address recorded in the AAPE data is a person's residence address for the possibility that their residence is not included in the AAPE data, while Methods B and C assume that one of the addresses recorded in the AAPE data is the individual's residence. We note that the Method A estimates are expected to underestimate population totals and are therefore more properly interpreted as a lower-bound on the population total. All three of these approaches produce tract level estimates, which we aggregate to the state level for the purposes of our analysis. For further details about these data, see Brown et al (2024).

The final demonstration estimate is produced using an approach called "Calibrated Administrative Record Dual-Systems Estimation" (Calibrated DSE), which produces dual-system population estimates for the year 2020 using the 2020 decennial Census and 2020 administrative and third-party data. These estimates are then calibrated to national and state estimates from the 2020 post-enumeration survey, and moved forward in time using county growth rates or declines estimated from the population estimates program, and from administrative record data. Further details about this process are explained in Brown et al (2024).

We use these five types of estimates to calculate the 408 one-dimensional maximum ratios for the subgroup proportions, and each of their associated test statistics. We also calculate 51 multidimensional maximum ratios from the vectors of subgroup proportions, and the resulting test statistics. For each of these maximum ratios, we investigate several types of guesstimated ranges for the associated parameter θ and document their impact on our results.

3.1 Approaches to “guesstimating” the magnitude of θ

Because the true value of θ is not known, our goal is to find reasonable values $\tilde{\theta}$ to substitute for θ in the MRT acceptable error radius $\alpha \times \theta$. This is difficult because the MRT is only relevant if we are not persuaded that our estimates are accurate. For this reason, our suggestions will involve making various assumptions about θ . We propose two broad approaches for doing this, which may be useful in different situations.

The first approach is to use a known parameter value that is thought to be of similar magnitude to θ , which we will refer to as a "proximate known value." In our application, we assume that for each demographic subgroup, the state population proportion in 2021 is close to the state population proportion as counted in the 2020 decennial Census.

A second approach is to use some function of the estimates we are evaluating to estimate θ . In our application, we consider the maximum of our estimates $\hat{\theta}_{(K)}$ as a rough upper bound for θ , and the minimum $\hat{\theta}_{(1)}$ as a rough lower bound.

We also note that the American Community Survey 5-year estimates have known standard errors, which we use to construct 99% confidence intervals for our population proportions. We use the largest and smallest bounds of their associated confidence intervals as potential bounds for θ in our one-dimensional application. These approaches have the advantage that they do not require the availability of a proximate known value. However, they implicitly assume that the measurements we are evaluating are good estimates of θ , which is what we are trying to test.

In summary, for our application we use the following one-dimensional guesstimates for θ :

- Census (2020) - Assume that θ is equal to the population parameter for the indicated demographic subgroup in the indicated state based on the 2020 decennial Census P.L. 94-171 redistricting data.
- Minimum Estimate (Min. Est) - Assume that θ is equal to the smallest estimate of the population parameter for the indicated subgroup in the indicated state.
- Maximum Estimate (Max. Est) - Assume that θ is equal to the largest estimate of the population parameter for the indicated subgroup in the indicated state.
- Lower 99% ACS Confidence Interval (Lower CI) - Assume that θ is equal to the lower 99% confidence bound for the population proportion of the indicated subgroup in the indicated state, based on the 2021 5-Year American Community Survey.
- Upper 99% ACS Confidence Interval (Upper CI) - Assume that θ is equal to the upper 99% confidence bound for the population proportion of the indicated subgroup in the indicated state, based on the 2021 5-Year American Community Survey.

The goal of multiplying our test statistic by a guesstimated parameter value is to distinguish between cases where the test statistic $T(M_0)$ is large because θ is small and cases where an estimate is far from θ in absolute terms. This is of particular concern when attempting to flag domains of estimation where at least one estimate is performing poorly. Even when our guesstimates are wrong, they can help us accomplish this objective if they capture the relative differences in the magnitude of θ between the domains being compared. In such cases, one can flag domains with higher values of $T(M_0) \times \tilde{\theta}$ for scrutiny without assuming that the implied error values $\alpha \times \tilde{\theta}$ are correct.

4. Results

4.1 One-Dimensional MRT Results

We start by calculating the one-dimensional MRT statistics in each of the 51 states (and DC) and 8 demographics, and multiplying by 100. Complete tables of the MRT statistics are provided in Hall (2024). Table 1 summarizes the distribution of these values. We also do a set of analyses in which we intentionally introduce errors for the MRT to find. In particular, we halve the Hispanic (Any Race) AAPE Method B population estimate in all states, and include this “bad estimate” when calculating the MRT statistics. Table 2 shows the distribution of the MRT statistics after introducing these bad estimates, and Figure 1 visualizes both sets of test statistics, with subgroups ordered by their average state proportion in the 2021 ACS.

Table 1: Summary of MRT Statistics across all States and Demographics

Min	Q1	Median	Mean	Q3	Max
0.7	3.8	8.5	12.4	18.6	59.1

Table 2: Summary of MRT Statistics across all States and Demographics (with Bad Estimate)

Min	Q1	Median	Mean	Q3	Max
1.5	6.1	15.2	17.7	27.2	65.3

1-Dimensional Maximum Ratio Tests

Figure 1: MRT Test Statistics by State and Demographic, with and without Bad Estimate

The distribution of the MRT statistics across all states and subgroups is fairly wide, with high maximums and low minimums. Note that the distribution of MRT statistics shifts noticeably to the right when we introduce our bad estimates. Comparing the first and second columns of Figure 1, we see large increases in the MRT statistics that correspond to this change. The difference is especially evident in the Hispanic (Any Race) subgroup, where we introduced our “bad estimate,” but is also apparent for many states in the “White,” “Black,” and “Asian” subgroups. This is because the proportions of the eight demographic subgroups in each state are dependent, so that an

estimation error in one of the proportions implies an estimation error in at least one other proportion. In smaller demographic subgroups, such as "AIAN", "Multirace", "Other", and "NH/PI", the MRT statistic is large in most states regardless of whether the bad estimate has been added. This is consistent with our expectation that MRT statistic values will be higher when the population parameter is smaller, since a given error will constitute a higher proportion of a small parameter than a large one. To help interpret the MRT statistics, we calculate guesstimated errors based on each of our proxies for θ . We summarize the distribution of these guesstimates in Table 3 and visualize them in Figure 2. The guesstimates with bad estimates included are visualized in Figure 3.

Table 3: Summary of Guesstimated Errors for Proportions across all States and Demographics

	<i>Min Est</i>	<i>Max Est</i>	<i>Census (2020)</i>	<i>Upper CI</i>	<i>Lower CI</i>
<i>Min</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Q1</i>	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.05
<i>Median</i>	0.24	0.32	0.26	0.25	0.23
<i>Mean</i>	0.45	0.54	0.50	0.48	0.46
<i>Q3</i>	0.61	0.80	0.73	0.63	0.59
<i>Max</i>	2.70	2.96	2.80	2.96	2.95

1-Dimensional Guesstimates (Without Adding Bad Estimate)

Figure 2: Guesstimated Errors for Demographic Proportions by State (without Bad Estimates)

Figure 3: Guesstimated Errors for Demographic Proportions by State (with Bad Estimates)

Complete tables of guesstimated errors are provided in Hall (2024). Table 3 shows that for all our guesstimates, the median errors are around 0.25 percentage points, with an interquartile range between 0.54 and 0.72 percentage points. The largest guesstimated errors are for the white population proportion in the state of Oklahoma, where at least one estimate is guesstimated to be at least 2.70 to 2.96 percentage points away from the true value.

Figure 2 also shows that the minimum proportion errors are of similar size for all our guesstimates when no bad estimates are added. Figure 3 shows that when we add bad estimates, our guesstimated errors for the Hispanic (Any Race) demographic subgroup increase dramatically. . These errors seem concentrated in a cluster of southwestern states such as California, Nevada, Arizona, New Mexico, Texas, and Colorado, but are also apparent in states such as New York, New Jersey, Massachusetts, Maryland, Illinois and Florida. This is consistent with our expectation that halving the estimated Hispanic population would introduce larger errors in states with a high proportion of Hispanic residents. The dependence of the different subgroup proportions is also visible in Figure 3, which clearly shows the large guesstimated errors for the proportions in the Hispanic subgroup mirrored in the White demographic subgroup.

The exact values of the guesstimates should not be over-interpreted, since they rely on assumptions that are almost certainly wrong. However, if the guesstimates roughly capture the sizes of the

population parameters in each state and demographic subgroup relative to each other, then they are suggestive of where at least one of our estimates might have larger estimation errors. The closer we think our guesstimates are to the unknown true values, the better our guesstimated errors will perform.

4.2 Multidimensional Results

To account for dependence in the subgroup proportions, we run two kinds of multidimensional maximum ratio tests that treat all eight population proportions in each state as a single parameter. The multidimensional maximum ratio test reveals whether any combination $\mathbf{v} = [\hat{\theta}_{1,k_1}, \dots, \hat{\theta}_{8,k_8}]^T$ of elements from our estimates are unacceptable. The multidimensional MRT statistics and their associated guesstimates for each state are listed in Hall (2024). We visualize the results of the multidimensional tests with and without adding bad estimates in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Multidimensional MRT Statistics for by State (with and without Bad Estimates)

The multidimensional MRT statistics in the "Didn't Add Bad Estimate" column of Figure 4 show a geographic pattern that looks like what we observe for the "White" subgroup in Figure 1 when no bad estimates were added, and to the "White" guesstimates in Figure 2. Similarly, the geographic pattern shown in the "Added Bad Estimate" panel looks like the pattern we observed for the "White" subgroup of Figure 1 when the bad estimates were added, and to the "Hispanic" and "White" guesstimates in Figure 3. However, none of the states that were flagged exclusively in smaller subgroups, such as "NH/PI," "AIAN," "Other," and "Multirace" were flagged by the multidimensional MRT. Interestingly, without making additional assumptions about the value of θ , the multidimensional MRT statistics were large in the same states that had large guesstimated errors for at least one subgroup estimate.

Mechanically, we can explain this by noting that the numerator of the multidimensional MRT statistic will be dominated by whichever subgroups have larger discrepancies between the maximum and minimum estimates for that subgroup. In our application, this is generally the "White" subgroup since it is the largest. Thus, our results are dominated by the impact of a few large demographic subgroups in this analysis. We also note that the denominator of the multidimensional MRT statistic will always be greater than or equal to the denominator of any one-dimensional MRT statistic. For any element $\hat{\theta}_{g,k}$ of a g -dimensional parameter estimate $\hat{\theta}_k$, it should hold that $\sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^G \hat{\theta}_{g,k}^2} \geq \hat{\theta}_{g,k}$. This means that the multidimensional MRT statistics are less likely than one-dimensional MRT statistics to "blow up" because of the denominator being small. One way to interpret this observation is that the parameter we are estimating has changed from θ_g to $\|\theta\|$, and this parameter is larger.

5. Discussion

In this section, we analyze some of the results from Section 4 to understand why our multidimensional MRT statistics perform the way they do. We focus on making comparisons between the one-dimensional and multidimensional MRT statistics with a view to understanding how they might best be used.

We start with our observation in Section 4 that the multidimensional MRT statistics for proportions as visualized in Figure 4 resembled the one-dimensional MRT statistics for the "White" subgroup proportions in Figure 1. This might be explained by the way that the multidimensional MRT statistic aggregates the differences between the estimates of each component of θ . We can get a more concrete sense of this by relating the multidimensional MRT statistic to the one-dimensional MRT statistics in the following way. Let M_g be the one-dimensional maximum ratio for estimates of the component θ_g from the parameter θ . We observe that for each $g \in \{1, \dots, G\}$

$$M_g = \frac{(\hat{\theta}_{g,(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)})}{\hat{\theta}_{g,(1)}}$$

which implies that

$$M_g \times \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)} = (\hat{\theta}_{g,(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)})$$

This implies that we can express the multidimensional maximum ratio as the root of a weighted average of the squared one-dimensional maximum ratios:

$$\frac{\|\hat{\theta}_{(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{(1)}\|}{\|\hat{\theta}_{(1)}\|} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^G (\hat{\theta}_{g,(K)} - \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)})^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^G \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)}^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{g=1}^G M_g^2 \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)}^2}{\sum_{g=1}^G \hat{\theta}_{g,(1)}^2}}$$

Thus, the multidimensional MRT dilutes the impact of subgroups with smaller minimum estimates and/or smaller one-dimensional maximum ratios, which correspond to smaller one-dimensional MRT statistics. The impact of large maximum ratios for some subgroups can be averaged out over the other subgroups, particularly when the minimum estimates for those subgroups are small. In our applications, the "White" population subgroup is consistently the largest, and so are its minimum estimates. As a result, it has a disproportionate impact on the value of the multidimensional MRT statistics that incorporate it. This does not imply that other subgroups cannot impact the outcome. The impact of the errors we introduced in the (somewhat smaller) Hispanic subgroup can be discerned in the high multidimensional MRT statistics for southwestern states in Figure 4, for example. But the impact of high MRT statistics for the smallest subgroups such as "Other" and "Multiracial" is essentially invisible.

This interpretation might suggest that the multidimensional MRT will fail to identify estimation errors in all but the largest subgroups. However, when the subgroup estimates are strongly dependent, then an estimation error in one subgroup must be mirrored by errors in other subgroups. A large enough estimation error in one subgroup could increase the maximum ratio for multiple subgroups at once, preventing its effect from being averaged out. Further, because the denominator of the multidimensional MRT statistic is larger, it is less likely than the one-dimensional MRT statistics to "blow up" when subgroups have small estimates. Combining information about multiple dependent subgroups can give the multidimensional MRT an advantage over the one-dimensional version by yielding higher test statistics when an unacceptable estimate is present and lower values when one is not, even when estimation errors are spread across smaller subgroups. This is one explanation for why the states flagged in Figure 4 so closely match the states with high guesstimated errors for the "White" and "Hispanic" subgroups in Figures 2 and 3.

6. Conclusion

With this paper, we aim to raise awareness of the maximum ratio and its associated tests as tools for comparing multiple estimates. We introduced a multidimensional generalization of Tsao and Wright

(1983)'s maximum ratio test. We discussed the difficulties with interpreting the maximum ratio test due to the unknown scale of the parameter, and proposed several approaches to address this ambiguity under various assumptions. Finally, we applied both variants of the maximum ratio test to a collection of estimated population proportions for eight racial and ethnic subgroups in each US state and compared the results.

One-dimensional MRTs had high values in most states for smaller demographic subgroups. However, after multiplying these values by our guesstimates for the value of the unknown true population proportions in each subgroup, nearly all these high MRT statistic values seemed to be associated with low underlying estimation errors. If our guesstimates are correct, the high one-dimensional MRT statistics are likely due to small subgroup sizes in many states rather than large estimation errors.

We concluded that the multidimensional MRT is more powerful than the one-dimensional MRT when component estimates are dependent. When errors in one component of an estimate imply errors in another component of that estimate, the multidimensional MRT can find geographies (or domains of estimation) in which at least one estimate is unacceptable while minimizing confounding due to the impact of small underlying parameters. If there is no dependence, the multidimensional MRT performs similarly to an average of the one-dimensional MRTs weighted by the size of the component estimates. In theory, the multidimensional MRT can flag invalid combinations of estimates as unacceptable even if all valid combinations are acceptable, leading to false positives. However, we did not notice any such cases in our application.

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